

A Study on Comparative Analysis of Swiggy and Zomato in Coimbatore

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Abstract

This paper proposes a comparative study on consumer choices between two major food delivery websites. Platforms, Zomato and Swiggy. In a period characterized by a rapid growth in online commerce and gaining popularity. Relating to online food delivery services, it is important for the providers to be aware of consumer behaviour and preferences in the aim to remain competitive. The method of conducting a survey was adopted in order to gather data for the study among a sample of consumers, including various demographics and geographic factors. It analyses user demographics, usage patterns, satisfaction levels, preferences, and factors influencing the choice between Zomato and Swiggy. Methods for statistical analysis such as descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were used to analyse and to identify patterns and trends in the data. The results provide revelations to user satisfaction on various aspects of the platforms, including user interface, delivery time, food quality, and level of customer service. Furthermore, the study breaks down elements relating to consumer decision factors like pricing and promotions in quick-service restaurants. Reliability, and App Features. A comparison between Zomato and Swiggy helps in gaining insight into the pros and cons of each platform, to assist in strategic decision-making and service. The implications of this research also apply to both Zomato as well as Swiggy, along with all the stakeholders involved in the online food. delivery market, providing valuable insights that help businesses enhance customer satisfaction and maintain a competitive advantage.

Keywords: Zomato, Swiggy, Statistical analysis techniques, descriptive statistics

INTRODUCTION

Online ordering for food has been one of the most prominent and technology-driven sectors in the global food industry. Due to the use of smartphones, high internet connectivity, artificial intelligence technology, and online payment systems, the modern customer can easily place an order for his/her preferred cuisine that is located in nearby restaurants or cloud kitchens through the online application/mobile app as per his/her choice and requirements.

The new generation online platforms such as Swiggy, Zomato, Uber Eats, and other online delivery platforms have changed the way the customers deal with the providers of the food sector. The on-demand food market of 2025 encompasses not only convenience, speed, personalization, sustainability, and consumer experience but also cloud kitchens, contactless delivery, sustainable packaging, subscription meals, and health-centric menus. The whole system is designed on three main pillars: Order, Prepare,

and Deliver, which are made possible through technology that links the consumer to restaurants and delivery partners.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The food delivery sector in India has recently witnessed the entry of online food delivery portals, resulting in intense competition between the main rivals, namely Swiggy and Zomato. Both of the main rivals expend a substantial amount of money on the internet for marketing, discounts, and other measures in order to attract maximum customers. It has been observed that despite similar services, there is some difference between the customers of Swiggy and Zomato. Customers switch between the services of Swiggy and Zomato. This results in a need to have an understanding of the effect of these marketing techniques used by Swiggy and Zomato on consumers. There emerges a need for carrying out a comparison on the effectiveness of promotional tools used by this company in addition to its pricing structures and quality in delivering its services and

interaction on social platforms based on the current market.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This paper will try to uncover the preferences of the customers when switching over to the two most popular food delivery portals, Swiggy and Zomato. The paper will try to uncover the reasons why customers prefer to switch over to the other portal considering the convenience, services, price, and other facets associated with the switching process of the portals. The paper will try to uncover the manner in which the two portals make use of the knowledge of digital marketing to lure and retain the clientele in the fiercely competitive market associated with the portals of Swiggy and Zomato. Therefore, this research paper aims to carry out its analysis on marketing techniques used by Swiggy and Zomato in order to have an understanding of what drives the preference and satisfaction of these two along with market positioning based on consumer behavior.

OBJECTIVES

- To analyse customer choice and consumption patterns with regard to Swiggy, Zomato, and other food delivery services in the current digital age.
- To comparing the popularity as well as market perception of Swiggy and Zomato websites, an analysis of reasons for the preference of users for one site over the other would be done
- To assess the level of customer satisfaction and loyalty with respect to Swiggy and Zomato, based on their entire ordering experience.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

i. Sources of data

This data is based on Primary and Secondary data.

ii. Data Collection Method

• Primary data

This data is qualitative as well as quantitative. As a research tool, a questionnaire is used to collect data. Structured questionnaire is a document that consists of a set of standardized questions through google form

• Secondary data

Secondary Sources of Information was gathered from books, journals, the internet, reports, and industry publications.

iii. Area of the study

The region of interest for this study is the Coimbatore city and its surrounding suburbs, where the operational presence of Swiggy and Zomato will be considered.

iv. Sampling size

The current research includes a total of 50 respondents who are users of online food delivery applications such as Swiggy and Zomato. The convenience sampling approach is used to collect informations from respondents.

v. Period of the study

November 2025 – January 2026

vi. Statistical tools of the study

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi-square

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The research is grounded on a small sample size, which may not be a true representation of the varied population of users of food delivery apps. Furthermore, the research employs a non-probability sampling technique, which may result in a selection bias since the respondents are selected based on convenience rather than using a random selection technique

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

DR. Kamlesh Babu Gautam (2019)¹ “A Comparative Study of Zomato and Swiggy Marketing Strategies The research shows that both, Zomato and Swiggy have achieved rapid growth due to solid digital marketing however they use separate strategies Zomato concentrates more on SEO and mobile app growth, while Swiggy makes huge investments in paid search and customer service. While Zomato brings in more fresh customers, Swiggy is able to retain far more loyal and engaged users. Together, both companies dominate and compete in India’s online food delivery space.

M. Thiagarajana, M. Alagu Amirthab (2020)² “A study on comparative analysis of Zomato and Swiggy based on consumer preference in Karaikudi The work concludes that Zomato is the most

preferred among the users' applicability factor for food delivery service followed by 18–23 years age group due to more variety of restaurant availability and best quality service perceptions. Swiggy has a higher valuation. Further, Swiggy's value proposition is expedited delivery and deals but overall user preference and market share aspect tilt heavily in favour of Zomato. Customer selection is primarily determined by the quality of service and on-time arrival.

Dr. Shivansh Setia, Parth Makwana, Dr. Tapesh Kumar (2021)³ "A Dubey. comparative study of Zomato and Swiggy with special reference to their marketing strategies." Zomato users are for gaming Swiggy, A large share of users Zomato than Swiggy for food delivery and perceive its offers more positively. Social media and particularly Youtube is recognized as the most effective advertising channels for both, reaching their audience very often.

Ms.K.Dhanya, Ms.K.Sowmiya, (2022)⁴ "A Comparative Study on Swiggy and Zomato with Special Reference." This study concludes that most of the respondents are satisfied with food delivery services offered by Swiggy and Zomato, with overall satisfaction of about 80% being reported. Swiggy is the most preferred service by customers, followed by a close second by Zomato, and there is no significant correlation with respect to the usage of these services by customers pertaining to their age and income factors. The services offered by both Swiggy and Zomato are effective but require further improvement with respect to discounts, quality, and servicing offered.

Roshan Baa Assistant Professor (2023)⁵ "A Comparative Study of Zomato and Swiggy." Department of Commerce. In the research, it is determined that the preferred online food delivery service in Ranchi is Zomato, due to the overall satisfaction provided by the service. The next is also Swiggy, which is effective in the delivery services but not as preferred by the population as is the case with Zomato. Both are seeing massive growth due to their reliance on online services since the spread of the pandemic.

Swiggy:

Sriharsha Majety and Nandan Reddy started Bundl, which was an eCommerce platform for the courier service/shipping market in India in 2013, turned into a food delivery service after its relaunch in 2014. Following this, they asked a friend of theirs, Rahul Jaimini, who had previously worked at Myntra, to help them start a company named Swiggy, which was launched in August 2014. By 2015, Swiggy had expanded from only serving Bangalore to servicing eight other Tier-1 cities across India. When these developments took place, the food delivery industry was experiencing a great deal of instability, as numerous notable startups Foodpanda, which merged with Ola Cabs; TinyOwl, which became part of Zomato; and Ola Cafe, which is now closed) were all having difficulty Swiggy received \$80 million in funding led by Naspers in 2017, followed by a \$100 million investment in February 2018 led by Naspers and Meituan- Dianping. By September 2018, Swiggy's valuation reached \$3.3 billion and increased to \$3.6 billion by April 2020, when it raised \$1.25 billion from SoftBank, Prosus, and others at a \$5.5 billion valuation. With an additional \$700 million round led by Invesco in January 2022, Swiggy's valuation rose to \$10.7 billion.

Zomato:

On July 10, 2008, Deepinder Goyal and Pankaj Chaddah established a digital platform to list restaurants, which they named FoodieBay, while employed by Bain & Company. The next month, a mobile version of Zomato was launched. In January of 2020, Zomato acquired the India-based operations of Uber Eats through an all-stock deal, granting Uber a 9.99% ownership stake in Zomato. Following this acquisition, Uber Eats ceased the independent operation of its business within India and migrated its existing user base and restaurant partners onto the Zomato platform. Prior to the acquisition, the estimated market share of Uber Eats was under 5% of the overall market. As a result of this acquisition, Zomato's market share was projected to grow to 52%.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

4.1 Age groups using the applications

Percentage analysis

Demographic Factors	Category	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	28	56
	Female	22	44
	Total	50	100
Age	Below 18	4	8
	19-35	14	28
	36-45	25	50
	Above 45	7	14
	Total	50	100
Occupation	Student	7	14
	Private employee	13	26
	Government employee	20	40
	Business/Self-employed	10	20
	Total	50	100
Monthly Income	Below ₹15,000	6	12
	₹15,001 – ₹30,000	14	28
	₹30,001 – ₹50,000	25	50
	Above ₹50,000	5	10
	Total	50	100
City / Area Type	Urban area	15	30.6
	Rural	14	28.6
	Semi-urban	20	40.8

Table 4.2, Food ordering frequency on the applications

Ordering frequency	Responses	Percentage (%)
Daily	5	10
Weekly	12	24
Monthly	21	42
Occasionally	12	24
Total	50	100

Interpretation

The majority of respondents order food monthly (42%), followed by weekly (24%) and occasionally (24%). Only 10% order food daily. This indicates that most customers use food ordering services occasionally rather than on a daily basis

Table 4.3: General problems faced by the users while using the applications

Problems faced	Responses	Percentage
Late delivery	5	10
Limited restaurant availability	9	18
Order cancellation issues	9	18
Poor customer support	19	38
No major problems	8	16
Total	50	100

Interpretation

The pie chart shows that 38% of users faced poor customer support, making it the most common problem. Late delivery and limited restaurant availability were reported by 18% each, while 16% experienced order cancellation issues. Only 10% of users reported no major problems, indicating that most users face at least one issue while using the app

4.4 Chi-square table

Combined Chi-Square Table

Monthly Income / Ordering Frequency	Daily (O/E/ χ^2)	Weekly (O/E/ χ^2)	Monthly (O/E/ χ^2)	Occasionally (O/E/ χ^2)	Row Total
Below ₹15,000	1 / 0.6 / 0.27	2 / 1.44 / 0.22	2 / 2.52 / 0.11	1 / 1.44 / 0.13	6
₹15,000–30,000	1 / 1.4 / 0.11	4 / 3.36 / 0.12	6 / 5.88 / 0.00	3 / 3.36 / 0.04	14
₹30,000–50,000	2 / 2.5 / 0.10	5 / 6.0 / 0.17	12 / 10.5 / 0.21	6 / 6.0 / 0.00	25
Above ₹50,000	1 / 0.5 / 0.50	1 / 1.2 / 0.03	1 / 2.1 / 0.58	2 / 1.2 / 0.53	5
Column Total	5	12	21	12	50

Interpretation

The Chi-square test was conducted to examine the relationship between monthly income and ordering frequency of Swiggy and Zomato users. The calculated Chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 2.41$) is less than the table value ($\chi^2 = 16.92$) at the 5% level of significance with 9 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

This indicates that there is no significant association between monthly income and the frequency of ordering food through Swiggy and Zomato. Hence, customers across different income groups show similar ordering behavior, suggesting that online food delivery platforms are widely used irrespective of income level.

FINDINGS

- The study reveals that online food delivery services are widely accepted among respondents in Coimbatore, indicating a strong penetration of digital food ordering platforms such as Swiggy and Zomato.

- A majority of the respondents belong to the 36–45 years age group (50%), followed by the 19–35 years category (28%), showing that middle-aged adults form a significant user base of online food delivery applications.

- With regard to ordering frequency, 42% of respondents place food orders monthly, while 24% order weekly and 24% occasionally. This indicates that online food delivery services are

used periodically rather than daily by most users.

- In terms of app preference, Zomato emerged as the slightly more preferred platform, while a significant portion of users reported using both Swiggy and Zomato interchangeably, suggesting low switching barriers between the platforms.

- The analysis of reasons for choosing Swiggy shows that affordable pricing and fast delivery are the major factors influencing users' preference for Swiggy.

SUGGESTION

Based on the findings of the study, it is suggested that both Swiggy and Zomato should strengthen their customer support systems, as poor customer service emerged as the most common issue faced by users. Improving response time, issue resolution, and communication during order delays can significantly enhance customer satisfaction. Both platforms should also focus on maintaining consistent and transparent pricing strategies, as customers are highly price-sensitive and frequently switch platforms based on offers and discounts. Enhancing the accuracy of delivery time estimates and ensuring faster deliveries can further improve the user experience. Swiggy may focus on expanding its restaurant variety to compete more effectively with Zomato, while Zomato can work on improving delivery speed and operational efficiency. Additionally, personalized offers, loyalty programs, and improved app performance can help in increasing customer retention. Since users across all income groups actively use these platforms, marketing strategies should target a broad audience rather than focusing on specific income segments. Overall, continuous improvement in service quality, reliability, and customer engagement will help both Swiggy and Zomato strengthen their competitive position and achieve higher customer satisfaction levels.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlights that Swiggy and Zomato have become integral parts of consumers' lifestyles due to their convenience, accessibility, and variety of services. However, the suggestions derived from the findings indicate that there is significant scope for improvement, particularly in the areas of customer support, delivery reliability, and pricing consistency. By strengthening grievance redressal mechanisms, improving delivery time accuracy, and offering transparent and personalized pricing strategies, both platforms can enhance overall customer satisfaction and loyalty. Expanding restaurant partnerships, improving app performance, and focusing on long-term customer engagement through loyalty

programs will further strengthen their market position. If these suggestions are effectively implemented, Swiggy and Zomato can not only reduce customer switching behaviour but also build sustainable competitive advantages in the rapidly evolving online food delivery market.

REFERENCES

1. Swiggy Limited is an Indian online food ordering and delivery company, headquartered in Bengaluru. As of 2025, it operates food delivery services in more than 700 Indian cities, and quick-commerce services under the name Instamart in 100 cities. The company was incorporated in 2013. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swiggy>
2. Zomato is an Indian online food ordering and delivery service owned by Eternal Limited. Created in 2008 by Deepinder Goyal and Pankaj Chaddah, it began as a restaurant aggregator, providing menu information, user reviews, and recommendations, and expanding to more than 20 countries by 2015. In 2015, Zomato entered the food delivery market in India, which soon after became its core business. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zomato>
3. **Gautam (2019)** This study explains that both Swiggy and Zomato achieved rapid growth through strong digital marketing strategies. Zomato focuses more on SEO and app engagement, while Swiggy emphasizes paid promotions and customer service to retain users.
4. **Thiagarajan & Alagu Amirthab (2020)** The study found that Zomato is more preferred among young users due to better restaurant variety and service quality. Swiggy was appreciated for faster delivery and attractive offers, with service quality being the key deciding factor.
5. **Setia, Makwana & Dubey (2021)** This research revealed that a larger share of users Zomato over Swiggy because of its stronger brand image and perceived value of offers. Social media, especially YouTube, was identified as an effective advertising platform.

6. **Dhanya & Sowmiya (2022)** The study concluded that around 80% of respondents were satisfied with both Swiggy and Zomato services. Swiggy was slightly more preferred, and no significant relationship was found between age, income, and app usage.
7. **Roshan Baa (2023)** This research showed that Zomato was the most preferred online food delivery service due to higher overall customer satisfaction. Swiggy ranked second and was mainly recognized for efficient delivery services.
8. **Research Methodology-CR Kothari**, New Age International Publishers, ISBN-978-81-224-1522-3